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Sustainable Water Treatment: Regenerating Activated Carbon to Remove Emerging Contaminants

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The persistence of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs), such as per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and pharmaceuticals, in environmental water matrices, like surface water and groundwater, presents significant challenges to both the environment and public health. Due to their resistance to conventional treatment methods, these CECs can accumulate over time, posing long-term toxicity risks. This work will investigate the ecotoxicity of these CECs using multicellular organisms, such as *Daphnia magna*, to highlight the potential risks they pose to aquatic organisms and ecosystems, even at low concentrations.[1] Additionally, the regeneration of activated carbons using greener solvents, such as ionic liquids and eutectic systems, will be explored as a sustainable alternative to conventional ethanol and methanol solvents.[2] The effectiveness of these environmentally friendly solvents in restoring the adsorptive capacity of activated carbon for removing PFAS and pharmaceutical contaminants will be evaluated. By combining greener regeneration methods with an understanding of CECs toxicity, this work will provide valuable insights into more sustainable and effective strategies for mitigating persistent water contamination while minimizing ecological risks.

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